

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF COPPER HYDROXYLAPATITE AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sample No.	Wt%			Molecular Formulae	Mol. wt.	Density	Molecular volume ml/mole	g. atom ratio		Lattice parameter	
	Cu	P	As					Cu	P+As	a	c
1.	51.27	15.01	—	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{FO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1289.5	3.565	347.68	1.664	8.83	6.53	
2.	49.43	12.08	5.84	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{FO}_4)_{5.0}(\text{AsO}_4)_{1.0}(\text{OH})_2$	1283.42	3.580	358.50	1.662	8.98	6.65	
3.	48.52	10.41	9.15	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{PO}_4)_{4.4}(\text{AsO}_4)_{1.6}(\text{OH})_2$	1309.77	3.582	365.60	1.667	9.14	6.74	
4.	46.99	7.03	17.15	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{FO}_4)_{3.1}(\text{AsO}_4)_{2.9}(\text{OH})_2$	1366.87	3.612	378.40	1.621	9.30	6.85	
5.	45.33	5.69	19.77	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{PO}_4)_{3.3}(\text{AsO}_4)_{2.7}(\text{OH})_2$	1402.01	3.642	384.90	1.596	9.42	6.92	
6.	43.69	2.34	25.24	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{FO}_4)_{1.1}(\text{AsO}_4)_{4.9}(\text{OH})_2$	1454.71	3.680	395.30	1.667	9.56	7.02	
7.	42.28	—	29.91	$\text{Cu}_{1.0}(\text{AsO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	1503.02	3.702	406.00	1.666	9.64	7.12	

Results and Discussion

Results of chemical analyses and molar volumes of samples are given in Table 1. Molecular formulae for each of the samples was assigned on the basis of results of chemical analysis. Observed value of molar g. atomic ratio (theoretical 1.67) of Cu/P and Cu/As for end members and

$\frac{\text{Cu}}{\text{P+As}}$ for others and closeness of the values of

molar volumes of end members and those for intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members is to indicate the formation of homogeneous solid solutions⁶.

Homogeneity and crystallinity of the samples were further confirmed by the values of lattice parameters of the samples. It is well established that all the members of apatite family exhibit hexagonal crystals belonging to hexagonal bipyramidal class 6/m (space group $C_{6h}^{3/m}$). The lattice parameters showed unit cell dialation consequent upon the introduction of bigger ion $(\text{AsO}_4)^{3-}$ in place of $(\text{PO}_4)^{3-}$ ion in the apatite lattice.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Micro Amounts of Gold(III) with Fluphenazine Hydrochloride and Promazine Hydrochloride

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PROMAZINE hydrochloride, PMH, 10-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-phenothiazine hydrochloride was proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II)¹. A survey of chemical literature has shown that no attempt has been made to use PMH and fluphenazine hydrochloride, FPH, 4-[3-(2-trifluoromethyl)-phenothiazine-10-yl]-propyl-1-piperazine-ethanol-hydrochloride as spectrophotometric reagents for gold(III). The present paper describes FPH and PMH as new sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for the determination of Au(III).

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents: A stock solution of 400 ppm of gold(III) was prepared by dissolving gold(III) chloride (Baird and Tatlock, London) in dilute AnalaR hydrochloric acid and diluted to 1 litre to give 1M with respect to hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically by the hydroquinone method². Aqueous 0.2% solutions of FPH and PMH were prepared in doubly distilled water and stored in a refrigerator. A Beckman Model DB spectrophotometer with stoppered 1 cm silica cells was used for the absorbance measurements.

Procedure for the Determination of Au :

(i) *with FPH:* Transfer an aliquot of the stock solution containing 5-425 μg of Au(III) to a 25 ml

volumetric flask. Add 9 ml of 8M hydrochloric acid, 4 ml of 0.2% FPH and dilute to the mark with doubly distilled water. Mix the solution well and measure the absorbance at 500 nm against a corresponding reagent blank prepared identically without Au(III). The amount of gold in the sample solution was then deduced from the standard calibration curve.

(ii) *with PMH*: Transfer an aliquot of the sample solution containing 5-175 μg of Au(III), 5 ml of 5M hydrochloric acid and 3 ml of 0.2% PMH into a 25 ml volumetric flask. Dilute the solution to the mark with doubly distilled water. Mix the solution well and measure the absorbance of the solution at 516 nm after 30 min against a reagent blank prepared in the same manner. Calculate the amount of Au(III) in the sample solution by means of a previously prepared standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

FPH and PMH are oxidised by gold(III) in hydrochloric, sulphuric, phosphoric or acetic acid medium to a red coloured species which is believed to be a radical cation³. The stability and the sensitivity of the red coloured species depend on the nature and concentration of the acid medium. The sensitivity of the reaction of FPH in four acid media is in the order, $\text{HCl} \approx \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 < \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 > \text{HAc}$. The stability of the radical cation of FPH in 3M HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and HAc is 60, 5, 150 and 5 min. respectively. The sensitivity of the reaction of PMH in four acid media is in the order $\text{HCl} \approx \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \approx \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 > \text{HAc}$. The stability of the red species in 1M HCl, H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 and HAc is 60, 40, 35 and 5 min. Hydrochloric acid medium has been selected because of its low cost and less interference of a number of foreign ions. Nitric acid medium cannot be used as it oxidises FPH and PMH to red coloured species.

The electronic spectra of FPH, PMH, gold(III) and red species are given in Figure 1. The absorption maximum of the red species of FPH and PMH is 496-505 nm and 512-520 nm respectively. The absorption spectra of the reagents under similar conditions show that the reagents do not absorb appreciably at these wavelengths. Hence a wavelength of 500 nm for FPH and 516 nm for PMH were used in subsequent investigations.

FPH gives full development of red colour instantaneously in 2.5-6.0M HCl and PMH in 0.5-3.0M HCl after 30 min as shown by the constancy of λ_{max} . FPH and PMH do not give maximum intensity of colour below 2.5M and 0.5M respectively. FPH and PMH undergo slow oxidation above 6.0M and 3.0M respectively. The absorbance of the coloured species remains constant for 1 hr.

Fig. 1 ABSORPTION SPECTRA

- (A) FPH and PMH
- (B) Gold(III) chloride (4 ppm)
- (C) Radical cation of FPH
- (D) Radical cation of PMH.

A thirty and thirty seven-fold molar excess of FPH and PMH are required respectively for the full development of colour intensity. It is found that there is no change in the absorbance or in colour intensity of the red species if the order of addition of reagents is changed. The intensity of the red colour is unaffected in the temperature range 5-60°.

Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0.2-17.0 ppm of Au for FPH and 0.2-7.0 ppm of Au for PMH. The optimum range for the effective spectrophotometric determination is 0.63-16.70 ppm of Au for FPH and 0.63-6.90 ppm of Au for PMH. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values for FPH are 1.334×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 14.6 ng/cm² and for PMH 2.415×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 8 ng/cm² respectively.

The precision and accuracy of the method have been studied by analysing (10 times) solutions containing known amounts of gold(III). The relative error and standard deviation are -0.088 and 0.02 respectively.

The interference of a number of ions commonly associated with gold(III) has been investigated. The

tolerance limits for various ions are given in Table 1. The alkali and alkaline earth metals do

metals of similar compositions of the synthetic mixtures.

TABLE 1—EFFECTS OF DIVERSE IONS

Ion added	Amount of gold(III) taken,		Ion added	Tolerance limit ^a	
				(μg/ml)	
	FPH	PMH		FPH	PMH
Flouride	2000	1200	Rhodium(III)	16	14
Chloride	6000	5600	Osmium(VIII)	2	3
Bromide	13000	12000	Platinum(IV)	6	8
Iodide	1	0.9	Copper(II)	330	280
Nitrate	5000	7500	Nickel(II)	290	320
Sulphate	8000	16000	Cobalt(II)	170	200
Phosphate	18000	18000	Silver, I	190	8
Thiosulphate	0.5	0.4	Iron(III)	0.5	0.4
Acetate	6000	4500	Uranium(VI)	1130	1130
Citrate	6000	5000	Zinc(II)	1400	1500
Tartrate	5800	3500	Magnesium(II)	1500	1400
EDTA	2	2	Lead(II)	400	700
Palladium(II)	0.5	0.4	Arsenic(III)	70	50
Ruthenium(III)	1.5	3	Aluminium(III)	1300	1400
Iridium(III)	14	15	Molybdenum(III)	1900	1950

a=amount causing an error of less than 2%.

not interfere. The complexes formed by Pd and Pt can be removed by extraction with chloroform. The interference due to Ag(I) can be eliminated by precipitating Ag as silver chloride by adding sodium chloride.

The sensitivity of the proposed methods is more than that of 2-hydroxyl methyl-6-(5-hydroxy-2-hydroxy-methyl-pyran-4-on-6-yl)-pyrano [3,2, -b] pyran-4-8-dione (66 ng/cm²)⁴, methyl green (16 ng/cm²)⁵, hydrobromic acid (40 ng/cm²)⁶, 5-(p-ethoxy anilino)-5,6-dihydrouacil (50 ng/cm²)⁷, isonicotinic acid hydrazide (51 ng/cm²)⁸, thiocaprolactametraiodioaurate(III) (53.3 ng/cm²)⁹ and 4-(2-pyridyl-azo)-resorcinol (51 ng/cm²)¹⁰. The sensitivity of the present methods is less than that of (4-dimethylaminophenyl)(4-benzylmethylaminophenyl) anti-pyryl carbinol (3.3 ng/cm²)¹¹, pyronine G (2.03 ng/cm²)¹² and p-dimethylaminobenzylidenerhodanine (6.8 ng/cm²)¹³.

The recommended procedure was tested in mixture of synthetic solutions prepared in HCl medium (Table 2). The results indicate that the procedure described in the paper can be adopted in the analysis of Au in dental alloy or an alloy of noble

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF GOLD IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES CORRESPONDING TO NOBLE-METAL DENTAL ALLOY USING FPH AND PMH

Au taken ppm	Ag ppm	Cu ppm	Pt ppm	Pd ppm	Zn ppm	Au found ppm
2.00	0.20	0.150	0.050	0.050	0.050	1.99
3.00	0.30	0.225	0.075	0.075	0.075	3.06
4.00	0.40	0.300	0.100	0.100	0.100	4.00
6.00	0.60	0.450	0.150	0.150	0.150	5.98
8.00	0.80	0.600	0.200	0.200	0.200	8.00

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Preparation, Magnetic Measurements and Spectral Studies on Copper(II) Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases

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THERE have been numerous studies on metal chelates with ligands containing ONO donors, for instance Schiff bases^{1,2}. Previously we have reported³ the preparation and characterization of the transition metal ion complexes of the bidentate Schiff bases. Of interest in Schiff base complexes we report here copper(II) complexes of tridentate dibasic ONO donor Schiff bases derived from o-aminophenol and 3-chloro-, 4-chloro-, 4-methyl- and 5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone.